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**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
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INTUITION HELPS US TO MAKE DECISION IN COGNITIVE THINKING

Annotation. In this article deals with intuition and its role of scientific thinking with brain. The functions of brain and about to make a decision to choose truth of knowledge. It is known that intuition is a specific way of generating genuine knowledge, a complex phenomenon of knowledge. A long period in science came without knowledge of the mechanism of intuitive cognition. Is intuitive cognition actually a process of higher cognition, consisting of thoughts that go on in the brain, the matured product of imagination, or purely logical thinking? About this, we will consider the mutual differences between the brain and consciousness and dialectical, synergistic analysis so that we can come to a clear conclusion.

Key words: intuition, scientific knowledge, brain, the function brain, problem and to solve it.

ИНТУИЦИЯ ПОМОГАЕТ НАМ ПРИНИМАТЬ РЕШЕНИЯ ПРИ КОГНИТИВНОМ МЫШЛЕНИИ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается интуиция и ее роль в научном мышлении с помощью мозга. Функции мозга и о том, как принять решение о выборе истины знания. Известно, что интуиция — это специфический способ порождения подлинного знания, сложный феномен познания. Длительный период в науке наступил без знания механизма интуитивного познания. Является ли интуитивное познание на самом деле процессом высшего познания, состоящим из мыслей, происходящих в мозгу, зрелым продуктом воображения или чисто логическим мышлением? По этому поводу мы рассмотрим взаимные различия между мозгом и сознанием, а также диалектический, синергетический анализ, чтобы прийти к однозначному выводу.

Ключевые слова: интуиция, научное знание, мозг, функция мозга, проблема и ее решение.

INTUITSIYA KOGNITIV TAFAKKURDA QAROR QABUL QILISHIMIZGA KO'MAKLASHUVCHI OMIL SIFATIDA

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada intuitsiya va uning miyadan foydalangan holda ilmiy fikrlashdagi roli ko'rib chiqiladi. Miyaning funksiyalari va bilish jarayonida haqiqatini tanlash bo'yicha qaror qabul qilish. Ma'lumki, sezgi haqiqiy bilimlarni yaratishning o'ziga xos usuli, bilishning murakkab hodisasidir. Ilm-fanning uzoq davri intuitiv bilim mexanizimimiz mavjud bo'lgan. Intuitiv bilish aslida miyada paydo bo'lgan fikrlardan tashkil topgan oliy bilish jarayonimi, tasavurning etuk mahsulimi yoki sof mantiqiy fikrlashmi? Shu munosabat bilan biz aniq bir xulosaga kelish uchun miya va ong o'rtasidagi o'zaro farqlarni, shuningdek, dialektik, sinergetik tahlillarni ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: sezgi, ilmiy bilim, miya, miya faoliyati, muammo va uning yechimi.

INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the 20th century, scientific research began to develop on the interaction of the human brain and neurons in it, their functions. In this regard, neurophysiologists and neurobiologists have compared the human brain to a biocomputer, that is, a thinking machine, a computer processor performing important tasks, a flashlight. The mind, on the other hand, is an indirect Observer, an analyzer, has the property of being awake, a computer screen that registers the information given by the brain, compared to a flashlight. Andri Kurpatov believes that the whole life of a person is the process of work of his brain, his desire. Everything he perceives, everything he hears, sees, feels, thinks, all experiences and visions are in fact a mutual associative fear of neurons that travel in the brain, nothing else. So, the meaning of a person's life is his brain, if a person's brain turns off, then his life meaning also ends.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concepts of the brain and mind have differences and recommendations. The brain makes decisions in relation to consciousness faster, since it makes decisions faster without analysis, often its decisions end ineffectively. Automates daily positive, negative habits, as well as the brain is able to perform 30,000,000,000,000 (trillion) functions at the same time. He does not spend energy on automated functions, but is forced to use his existing energy in the production of ideas, thinking and thinking. The brain has a capacity of 280 quintelions. In this regard, he left the Fujitsu Computer behind. While the mind takes time to think, it makes slower decisions, but its decisions towards the brain become effective in nature. Consciousness sees Well how to work without haste to think for a certain time and draw logical conclusions. The mind registers thoughts, ideas and events in the brain as states and outcomes, preferring analysis and research. However, it is the brain that has the opportunity to automate positive habits in a person, it is a biological fear.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

While the brain is only 2% of the body's body, in the process of thinking and thinking, it consumes up to 25 - 50% of energy. That is why the human brain, in relation to abstract concepts and ideas, perceives facts more quickly, so that young sought-after researchers precisely in the process of practice, the index of appropriation increases.

Our activities and actions are guided by our thoughts. But do we always control our thinking? Nobel laureate Daniel Kahneman explains why we sometimes do irrational things and how we make wrong decisions. A person has two systems of thinking. When we make decisions, "slow" thinking is turned on, for example, in the process of choosing a product in the store. It usually seems to us that we are confidently managing these processes, but we must not forget that "fast" thinking is constantly running in the background behind our consciousness-automatic, conscious and unconscious.

The strength of the brain is measured by the result that the brain can bring. The action of neurons and associative processes in the human mind and brain have their own self-organizing system, that is, a synergistic phenomenon.

Secondly, you can interest the brain in solving problems that are important to you. There are at least two ways to study the brain with a map:

- anatomical (frontal, temporal lobes, parietal region, thalamus, etc.
- * functional (importance determining system, acting system and passive system • It is here that the system that determines importance is responsible for conscious decisions. Studies show that we can consciously solve the problem taking into account no more than 3 factors, and our conscious thought lasts no more than 3 seconds. "Conscious" means that here you are used to feeling like your personality, thoughts, mood.

Man has always sought to know the structure of the universe, the laws of development of what exists in it and phenomena. In the process of cognition, situations occur when a person unexpectedly, accidentally, in a situation where information is limited, it is necessary to make a quick decision, making his decision "as if it were foreseen", "just as it should be done". One such case is what we call intuition.

And the intuitive process is exactly in harmony with words and concepts, such as decision-making, logical approach, subtle intelligence, scientific thinking, correct reasoning.

What is decision-making in fact, why a person always faces some complexity, hesitation in decision-making, why decisions make fundamental bumps in a person's life. To questions such as whether decisions are made in a conscious process, or whether it first occurs in the brain, neurobiologists and neurophysiologists cite the following facts:

In 1983, Benjamin Libet held an experiment. What was required of the subjects was to raise one finger when they "wanted to work". At the same time, the electrical activity of the brain was measured using the EEG apparatus. The main discovery was that the change in brain activity occurred about 500 milliseconds

before a person raised their finger, while the desire to raise their finger occurs about 200 milliseconds before raising their finger. Thus, brain activity indicated that the subject wanted to raise his finger 300 milliseconds before he reported that he wanted to raise his finger. This result aroused such interest outside the psychological community, as it seemed to indicate that even our simplest conscious actions were actually predetermined. We think we are making a choice, in fact our brain has already made that choice. But this does not mean that this choice was not made freely. It just means that we don't know that we were making a choice at that previous time.

Here B.Libet observed 3 states: 1) desire; 2) impulse; 3) action. Initial desire, impulse and movement in the brain. Hence, Libet proved that decisions initially appear in the brain.

Wilder Penfield (1891-1976) was one of the most distinctive neurosurgeons of his time, defining the methodology of the medical field for many years. The doctor, whom contemporaries even called the "greatest of Canadians", devoted his life to the study of processes in the brain - trying to explain the phenomenon of the human mind, the human soul. The medical scientist's reflections on this topic and conclusions based on the results of numerous studies are unique and have not lost their relevance to this day.

Wilder Penfield wrote that in the opinion of our brain there is an excellent automatic sensory-motor computer, and again for scientific research there are mechanisms of high mental activity that are closely related to mental activity for a long time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in the process of intuitive cognition, the brain makes decisions, while consciousness confirms and explains them. Scientists recognize their own creative mistakes in the processes of scientific observation towards ordinary people and try to move forward. The role of dominates in intuition is also of particular importance. Alexey Alexievich Ukhtomsky, a physiologist who first introduced the theory of Dominates to science, talks about interesting facts about dominates in the human brain.

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